

Appendix: Collated results from conversations with students about conditions and interventions

Student key
Student 1 (Uganda) - male
Student 2 (Uganda) - female
Student 3 (Kenya) - male
Student 4 (Kenya) - male
Student 5 (Rwanda) - male
Student 6 (Rwanda) - female

Condition	What would you call this?	Intervention (preventing/tr eating)	Where would you go/what would you do for this?	What do you think works for this? (eg treatment, prevention, traditional/modern)	Do you know anything else about this? For example, have you ever had advice from someone else about this? (eg treatment, prevention, traditional/modern)	Is there anything you would like to know about this?	Is this interesting/rel evant/importa nt to you and other people your age? (Scale 1-5)	Mean score
Common illnesses								
Diarrhoea		Sanitation, handwashing	Pharmacy	Take some tablets – flagyl- buy in pharmacy	Caused by eating dirty food and water		3,3,5,3	3.5
Vomiting					Relieves body		3,3	3
Headaches	Headache	Take paracetamol, drink water, rest Take aspirin, Herbs		Paracetamol	Doctor, parent, pharmacist May be a sign of a serious problem		4,3	3.5
Stomach ache	Stomach ache	Drink water and lemon/water and papaya seeds/eat clay/eat charcoal powder	Learned from looking at other people – seems to work	Drink salty water	Caused by food poisoning Caused by food that is dirty or not prepared well		4,3,5,5	4.25

Cold/flu	Flu, Flu	Prevention: Taking Vit C						
Cold/flu	Flu, Flu	Treatment: Drinking warm water/eating onion/eating honey/herbal medicine. Fasting	Learned from other people Taught by dad. YouTube	Drinking lemons – we know this because people usually take lemons when they have flu. ‘It is said by many people and even the government encourages people to drink it.’ There are tablets. Some tablets do not work. There is some medicine here for drinking but sometimes it does not help – nothing works. Some herbs are stronger than some tablets for colds and flu’ Ginger, lemon and garlic – boil together and drink Eggs, eating tea of honey mixed with ginger	Common in rainy season. The way people behave it spreads easily. It especially attacks children.		3,5,5,5	4.5
Fever			Go to the hospital is best Panadol from chemist Go to hospital	Taking medicine, going to the hospital. This helps one to know the problem. The best way to treat this is to sleep under a mosquito net. Going to the hospital may be better. Some people bathe using some herbs. Using herbals. Pour cold water over head or get medication Panadol Take antimalarials	This is a symptom of different diseases.		4,4,5,5,4	4.4
Sore throat	Not all understood what this meant. Pain in throat	Take antibiotics		I have not heard of any (antibiotics) that are used in sore throat	Sore throat especially comes with cough and it is a sign of Covid 19		3,3,1,5,4	3.2

Earache		Take antibiotics			Some women develop balls in their ears Earache mostly attacks women Not very common		4,0,2,5,3	2.4
Hay-fever	Don't know what this is	Antihistamine					1,2	1.5
Cough		Cough syrup, herbal medicine	Pharmacy Dad taught her 'it would heal me'	Take tablets – strepsils – buy them in the pharmacy – he knows they are good because they are advertised on the television Ginger mixed with black tea and drink it while it is hot			4,5	4.5
Choking	Don't know what this is			Patting on back, drink water Drink water			4,2	3
Nosebleeds			Learned in First Aid at school	Lying down on your back. Run cold water on your forehead. Pour cold water over the head	Warm air is the cause. Sitting in the sun. Mostly attacks people who have the flu. It helps the nose to be free. Caused by too much sunshine		2,3,4,5,4	3.6
Cuts and wounds	Skin rash, wound	Aloe vera herbs, eating chilli	Learned in First Aid at school	Aloe vera is good for healing wounds and removing scars, it is the best. Most people use herbs. Some people apply salt on their wounds – I have seen people apply salt and the wound heals, or use medicine called iodine. Clean with methylated spirit. Wash with clean water and put on medicine that they buy in the pharmacy. Tie the wound with soft clothes			5,5,5,4,5	4.8
Burns		Cow dung, sugar	Parents	Aloe vera is used after to prevent scars from occurring.			3,5,3,4,5	4

				Put in cold water – learned this practically First put cooking oil, then sugar, then go to hospital and they give medicine				
Hiccoughs	Sepluu	Drinking upside down, spoonful of sugar		Drink lots of water. Drink water – it works. Drink water and slow breathing– it works	Very common.		3,5,5,5	4.5
Allergic reactions				Tablets Hospital Medicine	Common. Some are allergic to plants, fur, dust, some food, some perfumes		4,4,3,3,4,5	3.8
Diabetes		Prevention: Drinking lots of water		Exercise, good diet. Going for check-ups, exercising, eating balanced diet.	I hear it in our community. People talk about it. Affects big people but these days it also attacks young ones.		4,4,	4
Diabetes		Treatment:		Juice from banana stem. My grandma used it and got well	This is common		4,4,1,4	3.25
Asthma			Treatment in hospital Get inhaler of doctor.	Inhalers and some herbs. It is very expensive. Use inhaler. Avoid cold	It is very dangerous. It mostly attacks young children and some are born with it. Only some people have this. Anyone can get this		5,4,5,4,5	4.6
Epilepsy	Never heard of it. Don't know what this is – didn't understand 'fits'/'seizures'/'convulsions' Don't know what this is	Treat seizures by putting sugar on tongue		Avoid stress			4,4,1	3

Sickle cell disease			Go to doctor	Don't know any treatment	It is very common among children. There are few people who survive. Caused by a lack of blood in the body (thinking of anaemia)		5,4,1	3.33
Worms/flukes		Prevention: Wash food, avoid swimming in infected freshwater			You get it by eating half cooked meat. You get them through eating.)))))	5,4,5,5,1 (scores for prevention and treatment)	4
Worms		Treatment: Aloe Vera, herbs	Government Government	Kisanda, omujjaja Tablets from government for children – get them at school. Some herbs and syrups. Government supplies de-worming tablets to everyone monthly – everyone takes them)))))		
Back pain		Bed rest	Sometimes hospital	Massage, tablets Do sports and get antibiotics	Common in old people May be a sign of infection Caused by carrying heavy things, working too hard		5,5,1,5	4
Hookworms				Not really sure	In dirty water or places, rainwater		2,4	3
Covid-19								
Covid-19		Prevention: Vaccine, Ventilation, Face masks, social distancing, drinking water (with lemon/with		SOPS (Social operating procedures) Take ginger, lemon, aloe, garlic, herbals to boost immunity Wear masks, sanitise, no vaccine reached us yet but people want it Masks, social distance, ventilation	People are ignoring SOPS. Finding the right treatment based on people's personal claims can be kind of hard. People are trying out different treatments without any knowledge.		5,5,4,5,5	4.8

		salt/ with ginger)			People don't believe in the vaccine. They don't believe it works. They worry the vaccine will have a bad effect on them.			
Covid-19		Treatment: Inhaling steam, sunlight, hydroxychloroquine, dexamethasone, eating garlic	The ones in bad condition are taken to hospital for oxygen If it is very bad, you go to hospital.	Stay in quarantine/isolate Vaccine Drink lemon juice				
Healthy eating and living								
Malnutrition		Healthy eating Yes, like veg, carrots, fruit	Painkillers to treat it		Very common among children who don't get enough nutrients It is caused by poor feeding Vitamin deficiency is not interesting Don't know how to prevent it. People eat certain foods to give vitamins but in the villages they don't care. People get 'epartit' if they do not get enough vitamins (they could not say what this is'		5,3, 1,1,5,5	3.33
Rickets/Beri-beri/ Night blindness	Never heard of this	Sufficient dietary Vit D and Calcium/sun exposure		Take enough vitamins				

Scurvy		Sufficient dietary Vit C			Caused by lack of vitamin C and not eating enough fruit and vegetables		5	
Obesity (weight loss)		Healthy eating, exercise, green tea, carrots, apple cider vinegar		Treatment would be exercising You can avoid eating too much oil. Do more physical exercises	Yes, it's very interesting. Not interesting. It usually exists in old people		4,4,1,5,5	3.8
Difficulty sleeping		Valerian, milk and honey, listening to music	Buy sleeping tablets in the chemist. They can be prescribed by the doctor.	Trying to relax the mind when you are worried I don't think (there are treatments) since people don't take it that serious Take sleeping pills (don't know name), go to sleep early enough Some use alcohol, cigarettes, drugs	Difficulty sleeping happens when you are sick or worried		3,5,1,4,4	3.4
Muscle soreness from exercise		Prevention: Stretching		Doing warm-up exercises and doing some relaxing yoga after exercising Taking some rest	Very common, like after running		4,1,4,3	3
Stitch when exercising	Don't know the word 'stitch'			Trying to relax your muscles Rest. Bathing with cool water making you relax. Take painkillers			5,4,5 (but not sure they understand)	4.7
Underweight/Too thin							3,5	4
Safety								
Injuries in car-accidents		Seat belts		Use first aid kit	People here lack enough health services and communication. Road accidents are very common in Uganda – boda-		5,5,5,4,5	4.8

					boda with 1 or 2 people on driving on walkways People don't always seat belts			
Injuries in bike accidents		Helmets			Mostly motorcycles – people don't really wear helmets Motorbikes – no helmets are worn		5,5,3,2,3,4 (motorbikes) 4 (bikes)	3.7
Drowning		Water safety/swimming lessons			Mostly affects people in the villages Problem for adults and children		2,3,2,4,4,5	3.3
Pedestrian accidents		Road safety lessons	Usually taught at primary school – they try to teach us		Too common here Some roads have no walkways It happens especially on bad roads. We do not learn road safety at school		5,5,5,4	4.75
Skin problems								
Acne/pimples	Don't understand 'acne' Use pimple Does not know word 'pimples'. In kinyarwanda 'ibiheri'	Smashed avocado on skin, lemon juice, egg yolk, potato water, spirit, sugar.	Creams like clozole B but they don't work. Wash your face with disinfectants.	Aloe vera – It is a healing plant, even it works perfect on scars – this is true Herbal soap 'Duru' – even it works perfect also Lemon and other local grass (don't know word in English) – it works somehow. Use eggs – put them on your face and wash it well	It is common in youths It is among the worst things that can happen to you Many people use it and share with others		5,5,3,5,5,4	4.5
Warts	Don't know what this is. Don't know what this is. Don't know what this is						3,2	2.5

	'ibibyimba byo kunocyi'							
Eczema	Don't know what this is. Don't know what this is. I explained it is dry, itchy skin.		Most go to herbalists and some for treatment in hospitals		It mostly attacks young children		3,4,2,5,3	3.4
Lice	This is like dandruff.				Common in villages because of poor hygiene. Dandruff		3,5,3,1	3
Skin infections		Cows' urine. Creams from pharmacy and supermarket.			Caused by lack of personal hygiene. Happens to children in local areas because of lack of hygiene. Caused by sharing clothes		4,4,4	4
Eye problems								
Poor vision		Eye-glasses	Many herbalists treat poor vision – 'I think they work' Teachers and many other people told him this	Getting eye-glasses Going for check-ups. Eat carrots and seek medications. Eye drops. Wear glasses, stop watching TV, phone, computer, sun. Too much light. Prevent by eating green vegetables (Dodo) – many people say this	Common among old people		3,4,4,4,5	4
Pink eye))	Eye infection. Don't know what this is – thought it meant pale eyes.	Breast milk	You can buy drops in pharmacy	Eye drops	Very common		5,3,0,3,5	3.2
Sty)								

Teeth/gums/mouth problems								
Tooth decay		Flouride toothpaste		Regular teeth cleaning with toothpaste. Avoid eating sugary foods - taught in school and advised by doctors. Brush teeth with toothpaste. Stop using cold things. Toothpaste removes germs in our teeth	Occurs mainly in children due to overeating of sweet things and not brushing carefully. We know this because of practical experience		4,5,5,5	4.75
Toothache			Go to dentist	Herbal medicine in form of powder Some chew a branch of a plant eaten by termites. 'My aunt claims it works perfectly but I am not sure if it works' Painkillers			5,4,5	4.7
Cold sores	Don't know what this is. Don't know what this is						0	0
Periods, pregnancy and contraception								
Heavy periods			Some go to Dr for check-ups	Some don't go to school. I don't know any treatments. Take pain medication like ibuprofen or naproxen. Drink hot water – this sometimes works-my mum does this	I don't know anything about periods		4 (F), 0,0 (M) 5 (F)	4.5 (F) 0 (M)
Painful periods		Prevention: avoid cocoa and sugary drinks		Yoga exercises (from YouTube) – these help – 'I think it is the best option' Herbal medicine – I don't know the name, it's a powder I get from friends. Tablets – Panadol and other painkillers – learned about these from the clinic and school bal			5 (F) 0,0 (M) 5 (F)	5 (F) 0 (M)

No periods			After 16 yo, go to hospital to see if there is a problem		It may be caused by not eating well and having too much stress		3 (F) 4 (F)	3.5 (F)
Pregnancy		Antenatal care Don't know what this is. Don't know what this is.	I know that pregnant women have to go to hospitals Seeing the doctor	Drink herbal medicine, eat healthily and exercise, get immunisations, sleep under a mosquito net Eating well every day			3 (F) 4,5, (M) 5 (F)	4 (F) 4.5 (M)
Pregnancy		Contraception		Abstaining By using a condom	Advised not to discuss in Uganda		4,3 (M) 4 (F)	4 (F) 3.5 (M)
Mental health								
Depression/feeling very sad	I don't know what it means. I only hear about it in movies. Not sure what this means		The only treatment is going to a DR. See a doctor	Do something exciting. Don't know any treatments. Eat healthily. Having people who love you.	It mostly attacks stressed people Mixed opinions about how common it is – one says very common, the other says not at all. I think this is a problem in the brain. It may cause nausea, bloating, high blood pressure, aches and pains		2,2,3,1,5,5	3
Anxiety/feeling worried	I have never heard of it as a disease. I don't know its meaning.		Treatment is by consulting doctors	I think the best treatments would be relaxing. Yoga Meditation	This is a problem in the brain, triggered by stress or difficult times		5,4,1,1,5	3.2
Body image worries	Have not heard of anorexia – when I				It is not so common (M) Common, especially in teenagers and the youth – in girls especially		3(M), 4(F) 5,2 (M) 3 (M), 5 (F)	4.5 (F) 3.25 (M)

	explained, they said 'Yes, it happens.'				Worrying about body shape is interesting for adolescent girls. It is a mental health problem that can cause self harm			
					They know what we mean by mental health problems but think other people their age would not.			
					There are no other mental health problems that are interesting to them.			
Things that are bad for our health								
		Smoking tobacco	Learned about this in science		Mostly cigarettes. This is common. Mostly men. People keep on smoking even though they know the dangers. Smoking cigarettes causes lung cancer, difficulty in breathing and hallucinating. Many people smoke but not many people their age. Mostly cigarettes, often goes with alcohol. Smoking is very dangerous because it damages human lungs and causes death		5,5, 4,5,3	4.4
	Waragi	Alcohol			Waragi is very cheap, hence attracting many people. Some even take it		5,3,5,5,4,5	4.5

					<p>at school and it is hard for teachers to identify.</p> <p>Not many people their age drink alcohol. A lot of men drink alcohol. It is a big problem. They take illicit brew which is dangerous to their health</p>			
		<p>Drugs (Bhang, Khat)(Mugo, cananambisi, mayirungi are all smoked by people, shisha)</p>	<p>People visit rehabilitation centres</p>	<p>Guidance and counselling</p>	<p>Causes hallucinating and addiction. Makes people be awake for a long time. People find it hard to stop using it. It is addictive. Many people their age use these.</p>		<p>5,5,5</p>	<p>5</p>
	<p>Don't know what this is Have heard of this but don't know what this is</p>	<p>Khat</p>						
		<p>Shisha</p>			<p>Really expensive compared to cigarettes. It is a tube with smoke coming out. Changes someone's state of mind. Musicians use it in their videos. Rich people use it. People buy it from shops.</p>		<p>3,4, 5,5</p>	<p>4.25</p>
<p>Infectious diseases</p>								

Malaria		Prevention: bednets/screens	Advised by the MoH by TV, radio and internet Learned at school	Sleeping under mosquito net. Clear the bushes and remove stagnant water. Sleep under a mosquito net. Sleeping under mosquito net, cutting bushes around you, closing windows at evening time	The government usually provides them (mosquito nets) free. They work but sometimes people don't like them because they come treated		2, 5,5,5	4.25
Malaria		Treatment: artemisinin, herbal medicine	Go to doctor for treatment	Bathing Some herbal medicine Medicine from the pharmacy – they give it even before they get to know what is the problem Curative drugs like paracetamol and COARTEM Plastmol			5, 5,5,5,4	4.8
Chickenpox			Some of my mum's friends directed her to a pharmacy, that is where she bought it (aloe vera) for my sister	Aloe vera – it works. You just have to smear yourself. My sister had chickenpox and that is what they used	It is common, especially in young children and some adults I don't know any treatment. Children who are not vaccinated get it		4,4,3,3,4	3.6
Measles		Cows' urine		The treatment is by drinking some herbs and going to the hospital. We are given the vaccine at 9 months (one didn't know this). There are no treatments, maybe some herbs	It is not so common nowadays. The government has tried to immunise it Children who are not vaccinated get it. I don't know how to prevent it		3,5,5,3,4	4
Mumps	Don't know what this is Don't know what this is				Children who are not vaccinated get it. I don't know how to prevent it		1,1,3,4	2.25

Schistosomiasis/bilharzia	Bilharzia			Avoid walking in watery areas. Wear protective clothing during floods. They are taught this at school. Don't know any treatments. Avoid being in contaminated water	Don't know how to avoid this. Caused by freshwater and parasitic worms.	Don't know anything about this	3,4,5,4	4
TB		DOTs	The only treatment is going to the hospital. Go to hospital	They don't know any treatments. Avoid by drinking well-cooked milk, and water and food – learned from teachers	It is also not so common nowadays because the government has tried to immunise it.		3, 3,4,4,4	3.6
HIV/AIDS		Prevention:		By going for testing before having sexual intercourse with anyone. Avoid using blades, needles, sharp objects. Avoid sexual intercourse with someone who is infected. Use condoms. We are taught this at school. Avoid unprotected sex with an affected person.			4,5,3,5,5	4.4
HIV/AIDS		Treatment: Antiretrovirals, sleeping with a virgin		ARVs There is no treatment – we are taught this by teachers. ARV – taught this by teachers. Only God's mercy There is no medicine	Some people nowadays are used to it by taking ARVs and some herbalists have come up with medicine.		4,4,0,5,5	3.6
Other STIs	Syphilis, candidiasis, syphilis, chancroid, gonorrhoea				We learn about these at school There is many but I don't know its names		3,5,5,5,4	4.4
Rabies	Don't know what it is		I think the only treatment is		It is not so common here. Don't know anything about treatment or prevention		2,4,1	2.3

			by going to the hospital.					
River blindness (onchocerciasis)	Never heard of this Don't know what it is		Only treatment is by going to the hospital.		Have never heard anyone sick of it		3,1,1	1.7
Elephantiasis/filaria sis					Not common Don't know any way of treating or preventing		4,3,2,3,4	3.2

<i>Interventions</i>	<i>What do you call this?</i>	<i>Where did you hear about this?</i>	<i>Where do you get this?</i>	<i>What is it used for?</i>	<i>Do you know anything else about it?</i>	<i>Score for interest/relevance</i>	<i>Mean score</i>
Aloe vera		Learned this from research on YouTube At first, I learned from my friends and my aunt advising me to try it out. I also got		It is also used in hair growth It is good for weight loss and boosts immunity. Used when you have a stomach-ache. It works. My mother uses it. Don't know what else it is used for. Is used as centuries medicine, it is a plant used to treat many things.	You mix it with lemon juice and drink We have a plant at home – it looks lovely! It is a common plant here (Uganda) Some people process it and even pack it as aloe vera gel	5,5,3,5,5,5	4.7

		<p>information on the internet</p> <p>Learned about it from parents and teachers</p>		<p>Healing and softening. It is usually used to treat burns, stomach pains. It improves digestive health and cleans acne</p>			
Therapeutic touch	<p>Don't know what this is</p>	<p>Healing hands by pastors and even witch doctors. It works to those who believe. Sometimes it works but some just want money.</p>		<p>Very common in churches. She believes: 'I have seen many get healed. I think it is all about faith'</p> <p>I don't know about this. They do not know anyone who has tried this</p>		2,4,3,4	3.25
Vitamin supplements			<p>They are bought by my mom from the pharmacy.</p>	<p>I take them.</p> <p>Very important – prevents one from getting night blindness</p> <p>50 out of 100 people take vitamin tablets but we go first to the hospital to know our diagnosis and that doctor gives you the tablets to take.</p>		4,3,5	4
Drinking water				<p>Very important – drinking clean water cleanses the body</p>		4,4,5 (some misunderstanding about drinking water for health and the importance of clean water)	4.3
Fish oil	<p>Don't know what this is</p>			<p>People eat small fish (Enkejje fish) for measles</p> <p>People eat silver fish (Mukene) to improve their brains and grades and for healthy skin</p>		3	3

Herbal medicines	Mwarubaini Akech	Grandparents tell us about these treatments. Herbalist (in a herbal clinic) tells us about it – they are often very old people in the rural areas We learn about them from teacher	People get herbal medicines from herbal medicine shops. Here (Uganda), people usually use the herbal way and that's why many shops have opened to sell the products. The people who run the shops have knowledge about the herbal medicine. They usually have books for reference from their ancestors about the different diseases, causes and treatment. These shops are specifically selling only herbal medicine.	Mwarubaini – it cures any disease. Mwarubaini and aloe vera boiled cures disease. They do work Herbal medicine are plants that produce medicine like ginger, valerian, more Their families sometimes use them – sometimes they make them for themselves. Yes, they work.		5,4,5,3,5,5	4.5
Meditation				It is good for anxiety		5,5	5
Antimalaria medications			You get them from the doctor at the hospital	They are used to treat malaria. Do they work? Yes, yes I don't know any. We just use preventions like mosquito nets and cutting long grass They work to fight against malaria and reduce malaria transmission		3,4,5,4,5	4.2

Antibiotics		Learned about them from teachers.	You can buy them in the pharmacy – the doctor has to tell you what to get You get them from the hospital and the pharmacy	Very useful though I don't know much about them They are used to cure diseases eg malaria It is medicine that fights against bacteria infection. They work.		3,5,4,5	4.25
Antenatal care						5,3	4 (see also 'Pregnancy')
Smoking cessation						4,5	4.5 (see also tobacco)
Vaccines				Didn't know these can be used to prevent disease		1,5,3,4	3.25